

Reasons to Use Matrimonial Groups:

1. Could you tell me whether you posted a matrimonial profile for yourself/ [for someone else]?
2. Can you describe the motivation behind creating a matrimonial profile on Facebook for yourself/ [the person you posted for]?
3. Why do you use Facebook for matrimonial purposes? (why not dating apps or other matrimonial websites)
4. What other platforms do you use?
5. Do you have a preference for using any of these platforms?
6. Why do you prefer using Facebook for matrimonial purposes over other platforms?
7. How did you first learn about matrimonial groups on Facebook, and what made you join them?
8. What kind of information did you include in your/ [the person you posted for] matrimonial profile and why did you include this information?
9. What kind of information did you exclude/ refrain from sharing specific information from your/ [the person you posted for] matrimonial profile and why?
10. How do you decide what information to share (at all) publicly vs privately?
11. Do you know anyone personally who got married through these groups?

Reasons for Sharing/ Not Sharing Information:

1. Does your/ [the person you posted for] family know that you are a member of a matrimonial group?
2. What role does your/ [the person you posted for] family play in your search? How do their expectations affect what you share online?
3. Does your/ [the person you posted for] family influence you to share specific information? If yes, what and why?
4. What information has your family requested you not to share online, and why?
5. Has your/ [the person you posted for] family shared stuff about you/ [them]?

Threats Associated with Matrimonial Groups:

1. What potential risks should one consider when disclosing personal information on Facebook?
2. What privacy risks do you fear when sharing personal information on Facebook?
3. How do you deal with this when facing unpleasant emotions, like being harassed or disappointed?
4. Can you share any experiences where you've dealt with unpleasant situations online during the matrimonial search?
5. What motivates you to continue being a part of these groups?
6. What are the risks for the people who post online?

Trust Factors:

1. How do you determine if a Facebook matrimonial profile/post is genuine?

2. Can you provide additional examples of cues or indicators that affect your trust in a matrimony profile?
3. Have you or anyone you know encountered negative situations like impersonation, where others pretended to be them on the internet?
4. What warning signs or red flags do you watch out for to determine whether a matrimony profile is legitimate?
5. What kind of responses have you received to your profile so far?

Admin's Responsibilities:

1. What role do admins have in providing a safe space for sharing personal information?
2. How do admins maintain privacy and security in Facebook matrimonial groups?
3. How should admins communicate regarding privacy risks?
4. What are they currently doing / not doing for privacy?
5. How can the admin make these groups a safer place for everyone?
6. Have you had any privacy or security issues, and how did you resolve them?

Suggestions for platforms:

1. How can platforms like Facebook better support user's goals and privacy?
2. How do you think Facebook can support protecting user's privacy?
3. Do you have any suggestions for increasing security and privacy in Facebook matrimonial groups?